

**Action of Alkali on 4-Methyl- β -1 : 2-naphthapyrone
and its 3-Chloro- and 3-Bromo Derivatives.**

**Formation of *cis*- and *trans*-Hydroxy-
naphthylcrotonic Acids and a New
Naphthylpropionic Aldehyde
Derivative.**

By B. B. DEY AND A. K. LAKSHMINARAYANAN.

It has been shown (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1630) that 4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone yields on treatment with alkali a fairly stable acid (m. p. 146°) which, on account of the ease with which it could be converted into the original pyrone by such simple methods as treatment of alcoholic solution with HCl gas or crystallisation from boiling solvents, etc., was regarded as having the *cis* configuration. Confirmation of this view has, however, been lacking since all attempts to convert this acid into the *trans* isomer were unsuccessful. We have now succeeded in preparing by the method of boiling an alkaline solution of the pyrone with mercuric oxide (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247 ; Chakravarti, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 817), a new isomeric acid (m. p. 112°), which, if the previous interpretation was correct, should be assigned the *trans* formula. The latter, however, undergoes conversion into the coumarin practically with the same readiness and in the same characteristic manner as its *cis* isomer, and has, moreover, a lower m.p.—properties which seem to be in conflict with the traditional views regarding the relative stabilities and melting temperatures of *cis-trans* isomers. Although the allocation of configurations to the two acids by a comparison of their common physical and chemical behaviours appears thus to be difficult, we have observed an interesting point of difference between them in regard to their response to the stimulus provided by ultraviolet illumination which seems to be highly significant and to justify our previous conclusions. On exposing solutions of the two acids in dry chloroform under identical conditions to the ultraviolet rays of a mercury lamp, it was observed that while the acid (m. p. 146°), believed to have the *cis* structure, remained unaltered, the other isomer was converted to the extent of about 70 % into the naphthapyrone. The assumption which prompted this investigation of the action of ultraviolet light on the two acids was deduced logically from a consideration of the relative

energy contents of a pair of *cis-trans* isomers. If, according to general belief, a *cis* compound existed on a higher energy level than its *trans* isomer, it would be reasonable to expect that the latter could be induced to take up energy, when supplied in a suitable form, and pass into the *cis*-body. The conversion of the *trans* compound into the coumarin is, however, obviously effected through the intermediate *cis*-phase, and the absence of any change in the case of the pure *cis*-acid seems, therefore, to be difficult to understand. The true explanation of this difference would probably be found in the following reasoning. Assuming that the *trans*-acid is converted by an access of energy from the ultraviolet rays into the *cis* condition, it is conceivable that the process would induce an activation of the molecules so as to prevent the transformation from being arrested at this stage but causing it to proceed further until cyclisation to the stable coumarin molecules has been effected. In the case of the *cis*-acid, on the other hand, the non-existence of the initial stimulus or activation may be argued as the cause of the molecules remaining inert and unaltered. Further work in this direction which might help in differentiating between similar pairs of *cis*- and *trans*-acids is engaging our attention.

The results obtained from a further study of the action of alkali on the 3-halogeno- β -naphthapyrones have proved to be equally interesting. It was previously reported (Dey, *loc. cit.*) that 3-chloro-4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone reacts with hot alkalis in a manner entirely different from other 3-chlorocoumarins and yields not the expected furan derivative but a stable chlorocoumarinic acid (*cis*). On repeating this work under carefully regulated conditions we find that although the chlorocoumarinic acid is the main but not the sole product under the conditions employed previously, prolonged boiling with concentrated potash does result in the conversion of the major portion of the substance into the hitherto unknown methyl- β -naphthafuran carboxylic acid (m. p. 240°). It may be remarked, however, that the new observation is by no means inconsistent with the assumption previously made that the chloro acid formed in large bulk from the 3-chloro- β -naphthapyrone possessed great stability, though it had the *cis* structure and this rendered the first step to the formation of a furan derivative in this reaction, the elimination of a molecule of alkali chloride from the *trans*-chloro acid, difficult, if not impossible. The present work establishes the point that if the treatment with alkali be continued sufficiently long, a considerable amount of *cis-trans* con-

version actually takes place with the consequent elimination of alkali chloride and closure of the furan ring, thus:

Continuation of work in this field has also served to show that the original anticipation that this singular change of 3-halogeno- β -naphthopyrone into the corresponding coumarinic acid would prove to be general, is incorrect. It has already been shown (Dey, Rao and Sankaranarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 282) that the formation of a stable *cis*-acid is connected, in some way which is not clearly understood yet, with the presence of the methyl group in 4-position, since the unsubstituted 3-chloro- and 5-bromo- β -naphthopyrones yield only the furan derivative unmixed with even a trace of the *cis*-acids. We now find that the substitution of bromine for chlorine, even in the 4-methyl- β -naphthopyrone, leads to results of an entirely different but highly interesting character. No bromo-coumarinic acid could be detected even on boiling with aqueous alkali for a comparatively short period; on the other hand, considerable quantities of β -naphthafuran carboxylic acid were isolated. But the principal product was a new substance (m. p. 136°) which contained no bromine, dissolved in cold caustic soda and was insoluble in sodium carbonate. It yielded a monoacetyl derivative (m. p. 117°) from which the parent compound was easily regenerated by hydrolysis. The phenolic character of the substance together with the results obtained on analysis led us at first to imagine it to be the 3-hydroxy-4-methyl- β -naphthopyrone produced by the simple replace-

ment of bromine by hydroxyl. A careful examination of the product led, however, to the interesting discovery that it was an aldehyde of the following constitution :

The compound shows all the reducing reactions of aldehydes, yields without difficulty a well-crystallised oxime, a phenylhydrazone and a semicarbazone and is converted by careful treatment with ammoniacal silver oxide into the corresponding acid. The formation of such an interesting product, which we have not observed in any other case although the same reaction was carefully repeated with several other 3-bromo-4-methylcoumarins, can be best explained by the assumption that an intermediate unstable hydroxycoumarinic acid (*cis*) is first produced, and this subsequently loses CO_2 and passes into the hydroxymethylene (enolic) form of the aldehyde. The reactions are indicated in the following scheme :

The best confirmatory evidence of the constitution given above is, however, derived from the observation that a practically quantitative conversion of the product into 3-methyl- β -naphthafuran (m. p. 57°) occurs when an alcoholic solution of the aldehyde or of its acetyl derivative is saturated with HCl gas. The following scheme explains the change.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cis- and trans- Acids from 4-Methyl- β -naphthapyrone.

cis- β -2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylcrotonic acid (4-methyl- β -naphthacoumarinic acid) (Dey, *loc. cit.*).—4-Methyl-1:2- $\beta\alpha$ -naphthapyrone (m. p. 178°) (2g.) was dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), aqueous caustic potash (20%, 20 c.c.) added and the mixture boiled under reflux for 4 hours. After distilling off most of the alcohol, water (30 c.c.) was added, the solution cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The turbid solution slowly deposited the coumarinic acid in lustrous colourless plates which melted sharply at 146° with evolution of steam and passed into the original naphthapyrone.

trans- β -2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylcrotonic acid (4-methyl- β -naphthacoumaric acid).—The pyrone (2 g.) was dissolved in boiling aqueous caustic soda (2 g. in 50 c.c.), the solution diluted with water to 150 c.c. and red mercuric oxide (2 g.) added and the mixture boiled under reflux for 2 hours. On acidifying the cold filtered solution with 2N-HCl, it became opalescent and slowly deposited a pale yellow oil which after rubbing for some hours solidified. It dissolved completely in cold sodium bicarbonate, but on acidifying the alkaline solution, the same phenomena of turbidity succeeded by the separation of an oil which gradually solidified were reproduced. The process was repeated thrice when the oil solidified almost immediately and it was finally purified by precipitating its acetone solution with water, yield 1 g. The acid melts sharply at 112° with the sudden evolution of steam and then immediately solidifies. The

residue (m.p. 178°) is found to be identical with 4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone. Attempts to crystallise the acid from hot solvents or to esterify it with alcohol and acid led to its complete conversion into the pyrone. [Found: C, 73.14; H, 5.5; M. W. (by titration with baryta), 227.5. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.3 per cent. M. W., 228].

Action of Ultraviolet Rays on the Coumaric and Coumarinic Acids.

(a) *Coumaric acid*.—A cold solution of the pure compound (0.5 g.) in dry chloroform (50 c.c.) contained in a quartz flask, to which a drop of a solution of bromine in chloroform (0.05%) had been added, was exposed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours to the light from a mercury-arc lamp, the distance being so adjusted as to prevent any appreciable rise of temperature. The solution was allowed to evaporate spontaneously and the residue left in contact with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution for an hour. The insoluble residue (0.35 g.) melted at $168-70^{\circ}$, the m.p. rose to 178° by a single crystallisation from acetic acid, and was identified with the β -naphthapyrone. The bicarbonate solution, on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, precipitated an oil which soon changed into a solid melting at $110-12^{\circ}$, identical in all respects with the coumaric acid.

(b) *Coumarinic acid*.—On exposing a solution of this acid (m.p. 146°) in dry chloroform to the ultraviolet rays of a mercury lamp under precisely similar conditions and evaporating the solvent, a residue completely soluble in cold sodium bicarbonate and recognised by the usual tests to be the unchanged coumarinic acid, was obtained.

Action of Alkali on 3-Chloro-4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone (m.p. 135°): Formation of 3-Chloro-4-methyl- β -naphthacoumarinic Acid and 3-Methyl- β -naphthafuran Carboxylic Acid.

(a) The chloro derivative (0.5 g.) was boiled with 2N-NaOH until it completely dissolved (10 minutes) and the clear yellow solution heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. On cooling and acidifying, colourless glistening plates slowly separated. These were purified by dissolving twice in cold sodium bicarbonate and acidifying, when they melted at 149° simultaneously evolving steam and passing into the chloropyrone.

(b) 0.5 G. of the pyrone was boiled with caustic potash solution (20%, 20 c.c.) for 2 hours. On cooling the sparingly soluble K-salt of the naphthafuran carboxylic acid crystallised out. The crystals were dissolved in water and the solution acidified. The pale brown solid which was immediately thrown down was collected and purified by re-dissolving in sodium bicarbonate and acidifying. Two crystallisations from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) gave colourless needles m. p. 240°. The mother liquor from the pale brown solid, on standing, deposited a small quantity of the impure chlorocoumarinic acid (m. p. 139-40°) which was purified by twice dissolving in cold bicarbonate and acidifying. (Found: C, 73.79; H, 4.30; M. W., 224. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 74.34; H, 4.42 per cent. M. W., 226). The *ethyl ester* of the naphthafuran carboxylic acid, prepared in the usual manner, crystallises from alcohol in soft colourless needles, m.p. 100°.

3-Bromo-4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone (Bacovescu, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1280).—A glacial acetic acid solution of the pyrone (4 g.) was treated with bromine (3.2 g. in 10 c.c.), and the mixture heated on the water-bath until HBr ceased to evolve. The bromo derivative crystallised on cooling and was once recrystallised from acetic acid. The pure product weighed 4 g. (m. p. 145°).

Action of alkali on 3-bromo-4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone: Formation of 3-methyl- β -naphthafuran carboxylic acid and 2-hydroxynaphthyl-1- α -propionic aldehyde.—The bromo compound (3 g.) was boiled with 2N-NaOH (40 c.c.) for 1 hour, the cooled alkaline filtrate acidified with 2N-HCl and the flocculent yellowish brown precipitate, which had a peculiar odour, was collected and washed with water. It gave no tests for halogen. On leaving in contact with *N*-sodium carbonate solution for sometime only a part of it dissolved, and on acidifying the filtrate, 3-methyl- β -naphthafuran carboxylic acid (m. p. 240°) separated out, yield 0.6 g.

The carbonate-insoluble residue, which formed the main bulk of the precipitate, dissolved in hot water and crystallised on cooling in glistening rectangular plates, m. p. 136°, yield 1 g. It dissolves in cold caustic soda and an alcoholic solution of the substance instantly decolourises cold acid permanganate and readily reduces ammoniacal silver oxide and Fehling's solution on warming. (Found: C, 78.35; H, 5.64. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 78.0; H, 6.0 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine, crystallises from hot water in shining prismatic needles,

m. p. 117°. (Found: C, 74.56; H, 5.58. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 5.75 per cent).

The *oxime*, prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of the aldehyde with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide for 2 hours, crystallises from alcohol in small colourless plates, m. p. 182°. (Found: N, 7.01. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.51 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from acetic acid in clusters of pale yellow needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: N, 9.87. $C_{19}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 9.66 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* forms colourless needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: N, 16.36. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent).

2-Hydroxynaphthyl-1- α -propionic acid was prepared by warming an aqueous solution of the aldehyde with ammoniacal silver oxide on the water-bath, removing the excess of silver with hydrochloric acid and concentrating the filtrate. It crystallises in small needles which readily dissolve in water on warming, m. p. 156°. (Found: Equiv., 220. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires Equiv., 216).

Action of HCl gas on an alcoholic solution of 2-hydroxynaphthyl-1- α -propionaldehyde: Formation of 3-methyl- β -naphthafuran.—The aldehyde (1 g.) dissolved in cold absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with dry HCl gas until saturated and after 12 hours the alcohol was evaporated on the water-bath and the tarry residue repeatedly washed by rubbing with water when it solidified. It was left in contact with dilute NaOH for 1 hour to remove any unchanged aldehyde and then crystallised twice from 50 % alcohol (charcoal), as colourless needles, m. p. 57°. (Found: C, 85.4; H, 5.65. $C_{13}H_{10}O$ requires C, 85.71; H, 5.49 per cent).

The 2-acetoxy derivative, when treated in the same way, gave also a good yield of the naphthafuran.

Attempts were made to condense the aldehyde with acetone, acetophenone and ethyl malonate but without success.